

Challenges in System Level Testing

312
Responses46:02
Average time to completeActive
Status1. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to focus on **corner-case testing** to ensure high quality?

8. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively design **exploratory testing** to improve quality with no diminishing returns?

9. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to define the optimal coverage in **maintenance testing** to ensure high quality?

10. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to establish the **useful lifetime of a test scenario**?

11. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to mitigate **regression scope increase** not to endanger quality?

12. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to find **areas of increased risk** (defect prone) to be tested with more focus?

13. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to effectively **balance between CRT, CIT, and CDRT** test coverage?

14. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to build effective **defect prediction models**?

15. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to secure proper **competence ramp up** of test engineers?

16. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to accurately **measure test effectiveness**?

17. How **Important / Urgent / Difficult** it is to manage **duplication of effort** between test teams?

18. What **other challenges** do You see in System Level Testing?

126 Responses

47 respondents (38%) answered test for this question.

Latest Responses

"Test overlapping between teams. HW and test tools availability."

19. How long do You work in the Software Engineering field?

20. What is Your current role?

